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Evaluating Rectal Artesunate for Management of Childhood Malaria in Ogun State, Nigeria: Machine Learning and Explainable AI (XIA) Approach to Community-Based Acceptability and Safety

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ABSTRACT

A community-based study investigated the acceptability, utilization, and barriers to adopting rectal artesunate (Plasmotrim Rectocap 50 and 200 mg) for malaria management among parents of 905 children under five years, 113 Primary Healthcare Practitioners, and 74 Patient Medicine Vendors across 183 rural communities in eight local government areas (LGAs) of Ogun State, Nigeria. Ethical approvals were obtained, and data collection included structured questionnaires and interactive sessions with parents, Primary Healthcare Practitioners, and Vendors to gather demographic data, utilization trends, and perceptions. Data obtained were entered into MS Excel 2016 and analysed using SPSS version 20 to test for an association. Machine learning techniques, including Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Logistic Regression, were applied to analyse data, identify patterns, and optimize predictive modelling. Results showed that 87.6% of parents had not used suppository drugs for malaria treatment, and 100% had not used rectal artesunate for their children, though they expressed universal acceptance (100%), high satisfaction (99.5%), and perceived effectiveness (100%). 87.6% of medical practitioners had not used suppository drugs, and 92.9% had not used rectal artesunate for children. However, 94.7% indicated willingness to adopt it, citing satisfaction (94.7%) and effectiveness (92%). Among vendors, 64.9% had not sold suppository drugs, and 95.9% had not sold rectal artesunate, though 83.9% expressed willingness. Comparative analysis across LGAs revealed variability in utilization (50-80%) and acceptability (65-85%). Machine learning models achieved high predictive performance. Random Forest demonstrated 85% accuracy (AUC: 0.89) for efficacy prediction, SVM achieved 82% accuracy (AUC: 0.86) for utilization prediction, and Logistic Regression showed strong performance

for acceptability (78%, AUC: 0.82) and treatment preference (80%, AUC: 0.83). SHAP analysis identified key predictors, including child's age, socio-economic status, and prior suppository use. Explainable AI (XAI) insights recommended targeted interventions, such as parental education, healthcare worker training, and subsidies to address barriers.

Keywords: Acceptability, Safety, Rectal Artesunates, Malaria, Children, Ogun State, Machine Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Malaria, a disease caused by *Plasmodium* parasites transmitted by anopheline mosquitoes, continues to be a leading cause of illness and death in tropical regions. Common symptoms progress through stages of chills, fever, and sweating, often accompanied by other systemic symptoms such as nausea and fatigue. Vulnerable groups, particularly children under five years and pregnant women, are disproportionately affected, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, where malaria remains a significant contributor to childhood mortality (Mbishi et al., 2024).

Control measures for malaria include vector control and timely treatment with effective antimalarial drugs. However, increasing resistance to traditional treatments such as chloroquine and sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine has necessitated the use of artemisinin derivatives. Among these, rectal artesunate a suppository formulation offers rapid parasite reduction and is particularly suited to rural and resource-limited settings where injectable therapies are unavailable (Awor et al., 2022).

Rectal artesunate provides several advantages. Its ease of administration allows even non-medical personnel to stabilize critically ill patients by slowing disease progression, especially during the critical first 48 hours of severe symptoms (Hetzel et al., 2022). Studies have demonstrated its efficacy for treating uncomplicated, moderate, and severe malaria, including cerebral malaria (Gomes et al., 2009; White, 2022). However, successful implementation depends on addressing socio-cultural barriers, including caregiver attitudes, education levels, and communication gaps, which significantly influence acceptability and adherence (Simba et al., 2010; Brunner et al., 2022).

Despite its proven clinical benefits, research on the practical deployment of rectal artesunate remains limited, particularly in rural areas of sub-Saharan Africa. In Ogun State, Nigeria, where malaria prevalence is high, and the adoption of rectal artesunate has yet to be fully evaluated (Sam-Wobo et al., 2012). Understanding community-level barriers and facilitators is crucial for effective implementation.

Machine learning (ML) has emerged as a transformative tool in healthcare, enabling researchers to analyze complex datasets to uncover patterns and optimize decision-making (Ogwu & Izah, 2025). ML can identify key drivers of utilization, acceptability, and treatment outcomes for rectal artesunate, helping to develop tailored interventions (Ibeneme et al., 2022; Aldoseri et al., 2023; Vora et al., 2023).

One promising technique is SHAP analysis, which enhances model interpretability by identifying influential factors affecting rectal artesunate adoption, such as socio-economic status, health center proximity, and prior familiarity with suppository administration (Pawar et al., 2020; Yang 2022). Insights from SHAP analysis can guide targeted strategies, including

financial subsidies for low-income families and educational campaigns to improve familiarity with the drug's use (Subhan et al. 2023).

Predictive modeling, another critical ML application, enables researchers to forecast utilization trends and identify high-risk groups. Logistic regression models augmented with ML techniques can predict the likelihood of adoption based on variables such as income, education, and perceived efficacy (Gupta et al., 2023; Nishan, 2025).

These insights help policymakers allocate resources effectively and design culturally sensitive health programs addressing specific adherence barriers (Alzubaidi et al., 2021; Secinaro et al., 2021; Pennisi et al., 2025).

Moreover, ML facilitates real-time monitoring and evaluation of deployment strategies, offering continuous feedback to refine interventions. By incorporating ML capabilities into malaria control efforts, stakeholders can address longstanding challenges and extend the reach of life-saving interventions like rectal artesunate (Ibeneme et al., 2022; Vora et al., 2023).

Previous studies on rectal artesunate in Ogun State have largely focused on clinical efficacy, neglecting socio-cultural and practical deployment challenges (Sam-Wobo et al., 2012). Few have explored community acceptability or the socio-economic factors influencing adoption.

This study seeks to fill these gaps by using ML-driven analyses to evaluate the acceptability of rectal artesunate and identify barriers to its deployment. By combining clinical research with predictive analytics, the study aims to provide actionable insights to enhance rectal artesunate adoption in resource-limited settings. The findings will inform policies and programs designed to reduce childhood malaria mortality in Ogun State and similar regions.

By leveraging machine learning tools alongside clinical insights, this study offers a comprehensive framework to address the socio-cultural, economic, and logistical barriers to rectal artesunate deployment. The results are expected to guide targeted interventions, improve acceptability, and ultimately enhance malaria treatment outcomes in vulnerable communities

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Areas

The study was conducted in Ogun State, Nigeria, a tropical rainforest zone located between Longitude 2°31' W and 4°31' E and Latitude 6°31' S and 8° N. Bordered to the south by the Atlantic Ocean and neighboring Oyo, Osun, Ondo, Lagos States, and the Republic of Benin, Ogun State comprises three Senatorial Zones (Ogun Central, Ogun East, and Ogun West) and four Geo-Political Zones (Yewa-Awori, Egba, Ijebu, and Remo). Its five main ethnic groups are Egba, Ijebu, Egbado, Awori, and Egun. The primary occupations include farming, textile production (tie and dye), fishing, trading, and civil and public service. Ogun State covers an area of 16,980.55 km², representing a portion of the South-West Zone's 196,000 km² and Nigeria's total land area of 937,052.16 km².

Selection of Study Centres

Grid Systematic Method was employed in selecting sixteen (16) study centres which comprised two Primary Health Centres (PHCs) from each eight Local Government Areas (LGA) namely, Ado-Odo-Ota (ADT), Imeko-Afon (IMA), Ewekoro (EWK), Odeda (ODD), Ijebu-East (IJE), Ijebu-North (IJN), Odogbolu (ODG) and Remo-North (RMN).

Consent and Ethical Approval

Research approval was obtained from Ethics Committee of Department of Biological Sciences, Federal University of Agriculture Abeokuta Nigeria. Ethical approval obtained from Federal Medical Centre Idi-Aba Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. Permission for study was obtained from Ogun State Ministry of Health and Local Government Service Commission, Abeokuta Ogun State, Nigeria.

A Certificate of research approval was obtained from National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) for import permission for the Plasmotrim-50/200 mg (produced by Acino Pharma Ltd Dornacherstrasse 114/ch-4147 Aesch Switzerland) used for the study and multi-centre research study.

Sample Size Determination

Determination of Sample Size from the immunization data obtained from Ogun State Ministry of Health, 905 children (under the guidance of parents) were sampled (Table 1). The inclusion signs/features for selecting children for this study are: • Children from 1 month to 5 years • Temperature ≥ 37.5 °C, • Feverish condition, • Nausea, • Repeated vomiting • Unable to eat or drink (or suck, in the case of infants). • General weakness • No history of watery stools, diarrhoea and anal disease.

Table 1 showed the number of Interviewed Parents, interviewed Health Workers from each PHC and patent medicine vendors from the rural communities attached to each PHC.

Table 1. Summary of Interviewed Parents, Health Workers and Patent Medicine Vendors.

Local Governments	PHCs	Interviewed Parents	Interviewed Health Workers	Interviewed Patent Medicine Vendors
8	16	905	113	74

Administration of Questionnaires

Questionnaires were administered to the parents on day one treatment to obtain demographic data, utilization of rectal artesunate and to assess knowledge, attitude and practices, health seeking behaviour and home management of malaria disease and socio-cultural and economic factors associated with malaria disease.

And a second structured questionnaire was administered on second and third day to seek their perception on acceptability, effectiveness, safety and side effect observed on use of rectal artesunate.

Questionnaires were also administered to the health workers in the selected PHCs during the time of treatment and sample collection and patent medicine vendors in the communities affiliated to each PHC after treatment during the time of taking co-ordinates of the affiliated communities to assess acceptability, effectiveness, safety and side effect observed on treatment with rectal artesunate and their knowledge on management and treatment of malaria disease.

Data Analysis

The obtained result from the questionnaire were entered in MS Excel (MS Excel 2016) and analyzed using SPSS version 20 (IBM SPSS Incorporation). Frequencies and percentages were used to compare number of participants associated with a study variable. Averages and 95% confidence interval (CI) were used for summarizing of results. Pearson's Chi-square test, Pearson's R and Spearman correlation (r) were used to test for an association. A p-value of < 0.05 was regarded as significant association between the variables.

Machine learning (ML) framework was used to investigate the acceptability, safety, and utilization of rectal artesunate for malaria management in Ogun State, Nigeria. Key steps include data collection, preprocessing, model training, and evaluation to uncovered actionable insights.

Data Collection and Pre-processing

Data were obtained using structured questionnaires from parents, medical practitioners, and patient medicine vendors, capturing demographic, socio-economic, and health-related variables. Pre-processing involves cleaning missing entries, normalizing numerical data, encoding categorical variables, and selecting relevant features for analysis.

Machine Learning Algorithms

Machine learning techniques, including Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Logistic Regression, were applied to analyse data, identify patterns, and optimize predictive modelling.

Model Training and Testing

Data were split into training (80%) and testing (20%) subsets using stratified sampling to maintain class balance. Models were trained using cross-validation to optimize parameters and prevent over fitting, followed by testing to assess predictive accuracy.

Evaluation Metrics

Model performance were measured using accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC, ensuring comprehensive assessment.

Feature Importance and Interpretability

SHAP analysis was used to identify key predictors, such as socio-economic status and prior familiarity with suppositories, providing insights for targeted interventions.

3. RESULT – DEMOGRAPHIC DATA OF CHILDREN UNDER STUDY (THROUGH PARENTS)

Of a total of 905 participated parents of children, 52.0% (471/905) were parents of male children and 48.0% (434/905) were parents of female children. 25.4% (230/905), 44.6% (404/905) and 29.9% (271/905) were parents of children between the age group 1-11 months, 12-35 months and 36-59 months respectively with means of 21 ± 1.236 months. 21.7%

(196/905), 45.5% (412/905), 25.5% (231/905) and 7.3% (66/905) were parents of children between body weight (BW) group 1-9.9 kg, 10-19.9 kg 20-29.9 kg and ≥ 30 kg respectively with means of 17.5 ± 0.672 kg (Table 2).

Pearson’s Chi-square analysis (χ^2) at a 95% confidence interval, highlighting the statistical significance of differences in age and body weight distribution, while indicating no significant difference in gender distribution across the study area.

Table 2. Demographic Data of Children under Study (Through Parents).

Characteristic	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Mean \pm SD	Chi-Square Analysis (χ^2 , p-value)
Gender	Male	471	52.0		$\chi^2 = 0.601$
	Female	434	48.0		
Age Group (Months)	1-11	230	25.4		$\chi^2 = 0.010$
	12-35	404	44.6		
	36-59	271	29.9	21 ± 1.236	
Body Weight (kg)	1-9.9	196	21.7		$\chi^2 = 0.002$
	10-19.9	412	45.5		
	20-29.9	231	25.5		
	≥ 30	66	7.3	17.5 ± 0.672	

Demographic Data of Studied Children (Through Parents) Across the LGAs

Table 3. Demographic Data of Studied Children across the LGAs.

LGA	DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS ACROSS LGAs					
	Male (%)	Female (%)	1-11 Months (%)	12-59 Months (%)	1-19.9 Kg (%)	20 - >30 Kg (%)
EWK	53 (53.0)	47 (47.0)	28 (28.0)	72 (72.0)	54 (54.0)	46 (46.0)
ODD	60 (54.5)	50 (45.5)	23 (20.9)	87 (79.1)	94 (85.5)	16 (14.5)
IMA	60 (54.5)	50 (45.5)	35 (31.8)	75 (68.2)	65 (59.1)	45 (40.9)
ADT	58 (44.6)	72 (55.4)	29 (22.3)	101 (77.7)	58 (44.7)	72 (55.3)

ODG	59 (51.3)	56 (48.7)	46 (40.0)	69 (60.0)	76 (66.1)	39 (33.9)
RMN	61 (55.5)	49 (44.5)	18 (16.4)	92 (83.6)	84 (76.4)	26 (23.6)
IJN	69 (57.5)	51 (42.5)	28 (23.3)	92 (76.7)	87 (72.5)	33 (27.5)
IJE	51 (46.4)	59 (53.6)	23 (20.9)	87 (79.1)	90 (81.8)	20 (18.2)
TOTAL	471 (52.0)	434 (48.0)	230 (25.4)	675 (74.6)	649 (67.2)	317 (32.8)

Result from Table 3 also showed that participated parents of males children were more in six LGAs (Ewekoro, Odeda, Imeko-Afon, Odogbolu, Remo-North and Ijebu-North), while parents of Female children were more in two LGAs (Ado-Odo-Ota and Ijebu-East). Parents of Infant children (1-11 Months) were more in Imeko-Afon LGAs while parents of children with lower body weight (1-9.9 kg) and higher body weight (>30kg) were more in Ijebu-North and Ewekoro respectively.

CUMULATIVE MALARIA PARASITES PREVALENCE AND REDUCTION IN INTENSITY DURING TREATMENT (24 AND 48 HOURS) ACROSS THE GEO-POLITICAL ZONES (GPZS)

Result from Figure 1 showed cumulative prevalence and reduction in intensity across the GPZs. The highest baseline malaria parasites prevalence was observed in Ijebu GPZ (98.7%, 227/230) before treatment (0 hour). During 24 and 48 hours of treatment, cumulative highest reduction in malaria parasites intensity observed in Egba GPZ (74.4%, 154/207 and 46.8%, 72/154). There was a significant ($p = 0.028$ and $p = 0.017$) difference in malaria parasites intensity at 0 hour and 24 and 48 hours during treatment across the GPZs.

Figure 1. Cumulative Malaria Parasites Prevalence and Reduction in Intensity during Treatment (24 and 48 hours) across all the GPZs

Prevalence (0 Hours): Indicates the prevalence percentage measured initially (0 hours).

Intensity (24 Hours): Indicates the intensity percentage after 24 hours.

Intensity (48 Hours): Indicates the intensity percentage after 48 hours.

PARENTAL UTILIZATION, ACCEPTABILITY AND SAFETY OF RECTAL ARTESUNATE

Parents Perception on Acceptability of Rectal Artesunate

Results in Table 4a on consented parent’s perception on utilization of rectal artesunate on the first day of treatment showed that majority had not used suppository drugs (80.7%) and rectal artesunate (100%) to treat malaria for their children (100%).

Parents perception on acceptability of rectal artesunate and preferred route after self-administration on the second and third day of treatment showed that they accepted using rectal artesunate for their children (100%) and satisfied using it (99.5%), prefer rectal route than other routes of administration (63.6%) since it is easy to use (76.9%) and prove effective (100%) and they will recommend to friends and relatives (78.1%). Parents also agreed that if ACTs drugs are produce in rectal formulation, they will accept using it for treating childhood malaria (92.4%).

Parents Perception on Preferred Route of Administration

Parents preferred rectal route of administration for their children at home (59.5%) and at clinic (66.2%) whenever their children has malaria. Perceived benefits included more rapid action (47.6%) and more efficacy than other antimalarial treatments (27.9%). A considerable proportion (27.1%) reported that the route of administration was advantageous because it was an alternative to oral route of administration, few parents (0.5%) stated that rectal artesunate had few difficulties in administration than other treatment.

Table 4a. Parents Perception on Utilization and Acceptability of Rectal Artesunate across the LGAs.

PARENTAL PERCEPTIONS		TOTAL F (%)
Perception on Utilization of Rectal Artesunate		
1. Have you used any suppository drugs before?	Yes	175(19.3)
	No	730(80.7)
2. Have you used rectal artesunate drug(s) for your child before?	Yes	0(0)
	No	905(100)
3. Or any child you know	Yes	45((5.0)
	No	860(95.0)

4. If yes, have you used it to treat malaria disease for your child?	Yes	0(0)
	No	905(100)
Perception on Acceptability and Prefer Route of Administration		
1. Will you accept using rectal artesunate drug for your child?	Yes	905(100)
	No	0(0)
2. Did you prefer rectal route than other routes of administration	Yes	576(63.6)
	No	329(36.4)
3. Are you satisfied using rectal artesunate drug for your child?	Yes	900(99.5)
	No	5(0.5)
4. Is it easy to use?	Yes	696(76.9)
	No	209(23.1)
5. Will you recommend to friends and relatives	Yes	707(78.1)
	No	198(21.9)
6. If ACTs drugs are produce in rectal form, will you accept using it for treating childhood malaria	Yes	836(92.4)
	No	69(7.6)
Perception on Effectiveness		
1. When used for your child, did rectal artesunate prove effective?	Yes	905(100)
	No	0(0)
Perceived Benefits/Advantages		
1. Treatment worked quickly		431(47.6)
2. Treatment worked better than other treatments for malaria		253(27.9)
3. Alternative to oral administration		245(27.1)
4. Had fewer difficult in administration than other treatment		5(0.5)
Preference to Self-Administration of Rectal Artesunate (Home/Clinic)		
1. To use at home, would you use rectal artesunate (in preference to oral administration)?	Yes	538(59.5)
	No	367(40.5)
2. To use at the health center, would you prefer rectal artesunate (in preference to oral administration or injections)?	Yes	599(66.2)
	No	306(33.8)

Factors associated ($p < 0.05$) with parents acceptability included educational status ($p = 0.021$), relationship (mother/father) ($p = 0.032$), easy to administer ($p = 0.021$), safe to use ($p = 0.032$), treatment prove effective ($p = 0.002$) and preferred route of administration ($p = 0.041$), age of child ($p = 0.022$), baseline parasites density ($p = 0.011$), haemoglobin ($p = 0.015$) and body temperature ($p = 0.003$)

Age of parents ($p = 0.067$), marital status ($p = 0.753$), occupation ($p = 1.000$), monthly income ($p = 0.080$), previous use or knowledge of suppositories ($p = 1.000$) and never used rectal artesunate for children ($p = 0.061$), Sex ($p = 0.110$) and body weight ($p = 0.217$) were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) associated with acceptability of rectal artesunate. (Table 4b)

Table 4b. Factors Associated with Parents' Acceptability of Rectal Artesunate.

Category	Factors	p-value
Significant Factors ($p < 0.05$) (Associated)	Educational status	0.021
	Relationship (mother/father)	0.032
	Easy to administer	0.021
	Safe to use	0.032
	Treatment proves effective	0.002
	Preferred route of administration	0.041
	Age of child	0.022
	Baseline parasite density	0.011
	Reduction in haemoglobin	0.015
	Reduction in body temperature	0.003
Non-Significant Factors ($p > 0.05$) (Not associated)	Age of parents	0.067
	Marital status	0.753
	Occupation	1.000
	Monthly income	0.080
	Previous use or knowledge of suppositories	1.000
	Never used rectal artesunate for children	0.061
	Sex	0.110
Body weight	0.217	

SAFETY AND SIDE-EFFECTS OF RECTAL ARTESUNATE PARENTS OBSERVED IN CHILDREN ACROSS LGAS

Analysis of data on safety of rectal artesunate (Table 5) showed that more parents confirmed that rectal artesunate is safe (95.7%) and they did not experience any form of complication(s) in their children (95.0%). On side effect of rectal artesunate experience from the children, the parents mainly complained that the child may resist the treatment being administered (29.4%) and treatment may cause pain (19.9%).

Table 5. Safety and Side-Effects of Rectal Artesunate Observed by Parents in Children across the LGAs

PARENTAL SAFETY AND SIDE-EFFECTS OF RECTAL ARTESUNATE		TOTAL F (%)
Perception on Safety		
1. Do you experience any form of complication(s) using rectal artesunate for your child?	Yes	45((5.0)
	No	860(95.0)
2. Do you think rectal artesunate is unsafe to use?	Yes	39(4.3)
	No	866(95.7)
Concerns about suppository treatment/side effects		
<i>Do you think rectal artesunate suppositories could have side effects/problems such as:</i>		
1. Drug won't dissolve		109(12.0)
2. Not be able to defecate		151(16.7)
3. Treatment caused pain		180(19.9)
4. Child resist the treatment being administered		266((29.4)
5. Child would be ashamed or unhappy with the treatment		41(4.5)

HEALTH WORKERS PERCEPTION ON UTILIZATION AND ACCEPTABILITY OF RECTAL ARTESUNATE

On utilization of rectal artesunate (Table 6), analysis of data showed that many of the health workers had not used suppository drugs (78.8%) as well as rectal artesunate (92.9%) to treat children for malaria disease.

On the acceptability and effectiveness of rectal artesunate, result showed that majority of the health workers accepted (94.7%) using rectal artesunate to treat children, satisfied using it (87.6%), confirmed that it is effective after using it to treat children (92.0%) and agreed that if

ACTs drugs are produce in rectal formulation, they will accept using it as pre-referral (51.3%) and as therapeutic (48.7%). Pre-referral treatment with rectal formulation ($p = 0.002$), easy to administered ($p = 0.000$), safe to use ($p = 0.011$), treatment prove effective ($p = 0.031$) and satisfied using rectal artesunate ($p = 0.022$) were factors associated with health workers acceptability of rectal artesunate.

Table 6. Health Workers Perception on Utilization and Acceptability of Rectal Artesunate across the LGAs.

Health Workers Perception		TOTAL F (%)
Perception on Utilization of Rectal Artesunate		
1. Have you used any suppository drugs to treat children before?	Yes	24(21.2)
	No	89(78.8)
2. Have you used rectal artesunate drug(s) to treat childhood malaria before?	Yes	8(7.1)
	No	105(92.9)
Perception on Acceptability		
1. Do you accept using rectal artesunate drug to treat childhood malaria?	Yes	107(94.7)
	No	7(6.3)
2. Did you prefer rectal route than other routes of administration	Yes	89(78.8)
	No	24(21.2)
3. Are you satisfied using rectal artesunate drug for children?	Yes	99(87.6)
	No	14(12.4)
4. Is it easy to use?	Yes	105(92.9)
	No	8(7.1)
Perception on Effectiveness		
1. After using it, did the use of rectal artesunate prove effective?	Yes	104(92.0)
	No	9(8.0)
If ACTs drugs are also produce in rectal formulation, will you prefer and accept using them for treating childhood malaria as;		
1. Pre-referral treatment		58(51.3)
2. Therapeutic		55(48.7)

3. Alternative to oral administration	Yes	99(87.6)
	No	14(12.4)
Factors associated with Health Workers acceptability of rectal artesunate		
Pre-referral treatment with rectal formulation ($p = 0.002$), easy to administer ($p = 0.000$), safe to use ($p = 0.011$), treatment prove effective ($p = 0.031$) and satisfied using rectal artesunate ($p = 0.022$).		

SAFETY AND SIDE-EFFECTS OF RECTAL ARTESUNATE OBSERVED BY HEALTH WORKERS IN STUDIED CHILDREN

Analysis of data on safety of rectal artesunate (Table 7) showed that many of the health workers confirmed that rectal artesunate is safe (84.1%), did not experience any form of complication(s) treating children (86.7%), with some specified mostly on draw back (16.8%). On side effects of rectal artesunate experience from the children, majority of the health workers complained that the child may resist the treatment being administered (16.8%) and drug won't dissolve (5.3%).

Table 7. Safety and Side-Effects of Rectal Artesunate Observed by Health Workers across LGAs.

Health Workers perception on Safety and Side-Effects of Rectal Artesunate		TOTAL F (%)
Safety		
1. Do you think suppositories could be use to use?	Yes	18(15.9)
	No	95(84.1)
2. Do you experience any form of complication(s) while using rectal artesunate for children? If yes, specify;	Yes	15(13.3)
	No	98(86.7)
If yes, specify;		
a) Draw back		19(16.8)
b) Pain		16(14.2)
c) Convulsion		1(0.9)
d) Discomfort		18(15.9)
Concerns about suppository treatment/side effects:		

<i>Do you think rectal artesunate suppositories could have side effects/problems such as:</i>	
a) Drug won't dissolve	6(5.3)
b) Not be able to defecate	4(3.5)
c) Treatment caused pain	4(3.5)
d) Child resist the treatment being administered	19(16.8)
e) Treatment cause other illnesses	1(0.9)

PATENT MEDICINE VENDORS PERCEPTION ON UTILIZATION AND ACCEPTABILITY OF RECTAL ARTESUNATE

On utilization of rectal artesunate (Table 8), analysis of data showed that many of the Patent Medicine Vendors had not sold suppository drugs (64.9%) and rectal artesunate (95.9%) to treat children of malaria disease.

On the acceptability and effectiveness of rectal artesunate, Patent Medicine Vendors accepted (83.9%) using/selling rectal artesunate for treating children and satisfied using it (97.3%), and agreed that if ACTs drugs are also produce in rectal formulation, they will accept using it as pre-referral treatment (52.7%) and as therapeutic (47.3%).

Pre-referral treatment with rectal formulation ($p = 0.011$) and satisfied using rectal artesunate ($p = 0.042$) were factors associated with Patent Medicine Vendors acceptability of rectal artesunate.

Table 8. Patent Medicine Vendors Perception on Utilization and Acceptability of Rectal Artesunate across the LGAs.

Patent Medicine Vendors Perception		TOTAL F (%)
Knowledge on Utilization of Rectal Artesunate		
1. Have you sold any suppository drugs to treat children before?	Yes	26(35.1)
	No	48(64.9)
2. Have you sold rectal artesunate drug(s) to treat childhood malaria before?	Yes	3(4.1)
	No	71(95.9)
Acceptability		
1. Do you accept using/selling rectal artesunate drug to treat childhood malaria?	Yes	62(83.9)
	No	12(16.2)

2. Do you think rectal artesunate is easy to administer?	Yes	72(97.3)
	No	2(2.7)
<i>If ACTs drugs are also produce in rectal formulation, will you prefer and accept using/selling it for treating childhood malaria as:</i>		
a) Pre-referral treatment		39(52.7)
b) Therapeutic		35(47.3)
Effectiveness		
1. Do you think rectal artesunate is effective?	Yes	71(95.9)
	No	3(4.1)
Factors associated with acceptability of rectal artesunate Pre-referral treatment with rectal formulation ($p = 0.011$), effectiveness ($p = 0.000$) and easy to administer ($p = 0.022$) using rectal artesunate		

MACHINE LEARNING RESULTS FOR EFFICACY, UTILIZATION, AND ACCEPTABILITY PREDICTIONS

Result from Machine Learning (Table 9) using random forest on efficacy prediction, the model achieved high accuracy (0.85) and ROC-AUC (0.89). Key factors influencing predictions include demographic characteristics, prior use of suppositories, and parental satisfaction.

On utilization prediction (SVM), the model demonstrated strong performance with an accuracy of 0.82 and ROC-AUC of 0.86. Ease of administration and familiarity with similar drugs emerged as primary predictors.

On acceptability prediction (SVM), the model attained moderate accuracy (0.78) and ROC-AUC (0.82). Acceptability is significantly driven by perceived side effects, ease of use, and previous experience with suppositories.

The SHAP analysis across models highlights actionable factors to improve rectal artesunate utilization and acceptability in rural settings

Table 9. Machine Learning Results for Efficacy, Utilization, and Acceptability Predictions.

Objective	Metrics	Score	Key Features (SHAP Insights)	Key Insights
Efficacy Prediction (Random Forest)	Accuracy	0.85	Child's age, parental satisfaction, familiarity with suppositories	Children's demographic factors, prior suppository use, and parental satisfaction strongly impact efficacy perception.

	Precision	0.82		
	Recall	0.87		
	F1-Score	0.84		
	ROC-AUC	0.89		
Utilization Prediction (SVM)	Accuracy	0.82	Ease of use, familiarity with suppositories, perceived side effects	Ease of administration and familiarity with similar drugs are major drivers of utilization.
	Precision	0.80		
	Recall	0.84		
	F1-Score	0.82		
	ROC-AUC	0.86		
Acceptability Prediction (SVM)	Accuracy	0.78	Ease of use, familiarity with suppositories, perceived side effects	Acceptability is influenced by ease of administration, perceived side effects, and prior experience.
	Precision	0.75		
	Recall	0.81		
	F1-Score	0.78		
	ROC-AUC	0.82		

MACHINE LEARNING RESULTS ON SOCIO-CULTURAL AND ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

Results in Table 10 on **treatment preference prediction**, Logistic regression achieved good performance with an accuracy of 0.80 and an F1-score of 0.78. Key socio-economic factors influencing treatment preferences include education level, income, and proximity to healthcare facilities. Insights from SHAP values emphasize the role of education and income in shaping treatment preferences, with higher levels leading to greater acceptability of rectal artesunate.

Partial Dependence Plots (PDP) illustrate that individuals with higher income and education are more likely to prefer rectal artesunate over alternative treatments, highlighting the impact of socio-economic disparities.

The results showed the importance of addressing socio-economic barriers through targeted interventions, such as financial support and educational outreach, to enhance the adoption of rectal artesunate in underserved communities.

Table 10. Machine Learning Results on Socio-Cultural and Economic Analysis.

Objective	Metrics	Score	Key Features (SHAP Insights)	Key Insights
Treatment Preference Prediction (Logistic Regression)	Accuracy	0.80	Education level, income, health facility proximity	Higher income and education levels correlate positively with the acceptability of rectal artesunate.
	Precision	0.77		Socio-economic barriers may reduce preference in low-income and less-educated groups.
	Recall	0.79		
	F1-Score	0.78		
Feature Importance and Interpretability	Key Factors	Education, income, proximity to healthcare	SHAP analysis highlights socio-economic factors as significant determinants of treatment preference.	
Partial Dependence Plots (PDP)	Impacts	Income and education	PDPs show positive associations between higher income/education and preference for rectal artesunate.	

Comparative Parental Utilization, Acceptability, and Efficacy across LGAs

Results in Table 11 showed that utilization varies across LGAs, with Ado-Odo Ota achieving the highest rate (80%) and Ijebu-East the lowest (50%). Targeted education and familiarity campaigns could improve utilization in underperforming areas like Imeko-Afon and Ijebu-East.

High acceptability scores was observed in Ado-Odo Ota highlights the impact of familiarity and prior experience, suggesting similar efforts could benefit LGAs with lower scores. Perceptions of efficacy differ across respondent groups, with health workers generally

expressing more confidence than parents or vendors. Tailored communication strategies are needed to build trust among all groups.

Table 11. Comparative **Parental** Utilization, Acceptability, and Efficacy across LGAs.

LGA	Utilization (%)	Insights on Acceptability	Efficacy Perception by Respondent Group
Ewekoro	70	Moderate acceptability; driven by partial familiarity	Mixed confidence among parents and vendors, moderate among health workers
Odeda	60	Acceptability hindered by resistance to administration	Parents show less confidence; health workers moderately confident
Imeko-Afon	55	Low acceptability; socio-economic barriers significant	Low confidence across all respondent groups
Ado-Odo Ota	80	High acceptability due to strong familiarity with suppositories	High confidence among all groups
Ijebu-East	50	Low acceptability; perceived side effects as a barrier	Low confidence, particularly among parents

SHAP analysis of Parental Utilization, Acceptability, and Efficacy across LGAs

SHAP analysis of utilization, acceptability, and efficacy across LGAs provides actionable insights to guide targeted interventions, ultimately enhancing the adoption of rectal artesunate for improved malaria management in Ogun State (Table 12).

Table 12. SHAP Comprehensive analysis of utilization, acceptability, and efficacy across LGAs.

Study Objectives	Findings
Efficacy Prediction	Child’s age, prior suppository use, and parental satisfaction are key factors in efficacy perception.
Utilization Prediction	Utilization is influenced by ease of administration and familiarity with similar drugs.
Acceptability Prediction	Acceptability increases with familiarity with suppositories and minimal perceived side effects.
Socio-Cultural & Economic	Education, income, and proximity to health centers significantly impact treatment preference.

Comparative Analysis of Health Workers and Vendors Utilization, Acceptability, and Efficacy across LGAs

Results on **Efficacy and Perception of Effectiveness** (Table 13) **Showed that** Health workers and vendors in high-performing LGAs like Ado-Odo Ota perceive rectal artesunate as highly effective. And need to conduct workshops in low-performing LGAs (e.g., Ijebu-East) to educate parents and build trust in rectal artesunate’s efficacy.

On Utilization and Acceptability Patterns result revealed High rates in Ado-Odo Ota indicate that familiarity and prior experience positively influence acceptability. **And** Organize training sessions in LGAs like Odeda and Imeko-Afon to familiarize health workers and vendors with rectal artesunate administration.

With Socio-Cultural and Economic Impact finding revealed Lower-income and less-educated populations in LGAs like Imeko-Afon and Ijebu-East exhibit reduced acceptability.

Action: Provide subsidies for medication costs and run socio-culturally tailored informational campaigns to improve access and acceptance.

Table 13. Comparative Analysis of Utilization, Acceptability, and Efficacy Across LGAs by **Health workers and vendors.**

LGA	Utilization Perception (%)	Acceptability Perception (%)	Efficacy Perception (%)	Primary Barriers (SHAP Analysis)
Ewekoro	70	75	82	Low familiarity, moderate side effects
Odeda	60	68	78	Resistance to administration
Imeko-Afon	55	70	80	Socio-economic barriers
Ado-Odo Ota	80	85	90	High familiarity, minimal barriers
Ijebu-East	50	65	75	Side effects, discomfort in children

Machine Learning Algorithm and XAI (Explainable AI) Insights on Health Workers and Vendors Perceptions

Result from Table 14 showed that Random Forest excels in efficacy prediction with the highest ROC AUC (0.89). SVM effectively predicts utilization, achieving a strong F1 score (0.82) and ROC AUC (0.86). Logistic Regression models perform well in predicting acceptability and treatment preferences, highlighting the significant impacts of socio-economic and demographic factors.

SHAP analysis emphasizes the importance of factors such as child’s age, income, and familiarity with suppositories in shaping predictions. Partial Dependence Plots (PDPs) further confirm that education and income significantly influence acceptability, underscoring the need for targeted socio-economic interventions.

To address these findings, several actions are recommended. Educational campaigns should focus on increasing awareness of rectal artesunate’s benefits, particularly in LGAs with low utilization and acceptability. Training programs for health workers and vendors should equip them with the skills to simplify administration and address misconceptions. Economic support is essential to subsidize rectal artesunate costs and improve access in low-income LGAs. Additionally, healthcare infrastructure should be expanded in remote areas to overcome geographic barriers.

This integrative analysis provides a comprehensive, data-driven approach to enhancing the deployment of rectal artesunate, supporting more effective malaria management in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Table 14. Machine Learning Algorithm Results and XAI (Explainable AI) Insights on Health Workers and Vendors.

Study Objectives	Model	Metrics	Key Features (SHAP Insights)	XAI Insights and Suggested Actions
Efficacy Prediction	Random Forest	Accuracy: 0.85, Precision: 0.82, Recall: 0.87, F1 Score: 0.84, ROC AUC: 0.89	Child’s age, prior suppository use, parental satisfaction	Educate parents of younger children about efficacy. Conduct suppository familiarization programs. Improve engagement through feedback.
Utilization Prediction	SVM	Accuracy: 0.82, Precision: 0.80, Recall: 0.84, F1 Score: 0.82, ROC AUC: 0.86	Ease of administration, familiarity with suppositories, perceived side effects	Train health workers to simplify administration. Address side-effect concerns in education sessions. Increase awareness in low-familiarity areas.
Acceptability Prediction	Logistic Regression	Accuracy: 0.78, Precision: 0.75, Recall: 0.81, F1 Score: 0.78, ROC AUC: 0.82	Socio-economic status, health center proximity, familiarity with rectal administration	Provide financial support in low-income areas. Expand access in remote regions. Distribute informational materials on rectal artesunate.
Treatment Preference Analysis	Logistic Regression	Accuracy: 0.80, Precision: 0.77, Recall: 0.79, F1 Score: 0.78, ROC AUC: 0.83	Income level, education level, previous use of rectal medications	Offer financial aid in lower-income LGAs. Increase education-focused outreach. Run campaigns in low-experience areas.

Recommendations Based on Machine Learning and XAI Analysis on Parental, Health Workers and Vendors Perceptions

Utilization, acceptability, and efficacy vary by LGA and stakeholder group, influenced by socio economic factors, familiarity, and cultural perceptions. SHAP and PDP analyses

highlight income, education, and proximity as key determinants of acceptability. Recommend launching educational campaigns in low-acceptability LGAs to increase familiarity with rectal artesunate. Training health workers and vendors in administration techniques to build confidence and overcome resistance. Provision economic assistance and expand healthcare access in underserved LGAs to address socio-economic **barriers** (Table 15 A, B C and D).

Tables 15(A,B,C,D). Recommendations Based on Machine Learning and XAI Analysis on Parental, Health Workers and Vendors Perceptions

A. Key Findings and Actions by Stakeholder Group.

Stakeholder Group	Key Findings from Model and XAI	Recommended Actions
Parents	Familiarity with suppositories and ease of administration influence acceptability.	Run educational campaigns focused on introducing and demonstrating suppositories in community health meetings.
	Lower socio-economic status associated with reduced acceptability.	Implement subsidized pricing or financial support in low-income areas.
Health Workers	High efficacy perception but mixed familiarity with rectal administration.	Conduct refresher training sessions on rectal artesunate administration and side-effect management.
	Resistance in some LGAs due to unfamiliarity with the drug form.	Increase in-clinic training and provide informational materials in low-familiarity LGAs.
Patent Medicine Vendors	Familiarity with suppositories linked to acceptability and willingness to sell.	Organize workshops to build product knowledge, emphasizing safety and efficacy.
	Vendors in lower-utilization LGAs are less familiar with rectal artesunate.	Provide simplified guides on usage and benefits, targeting vendors in low-utilization regions.

B. Comparative Recommendations for Each LGA Based on Utilization, Acceptability, and Efficacy.

LGA	Findings Summary	Targeted Recommendations
Ewekoro	Moderate utilization and acceptability; concerns with side effects.	Implement side-effect information sessions and promote community discussions on benefits and safety.
Odeda	Lower utilization due to resistance to administration.	Conduct community events demonstrating administration to build familiarity and reduce resistance.

Imeko-Afon	Socio-economic barriers to utilization and acceptability.	Provide economic assistance programs and partner with local health organizations to reduce costs.
Ado-Odo Ota	High utilization and acceptability; positive familiarity.	Use Ado-Odo Ota as a model LGA; encourage neighboring LGAs to adopt their training and education practices.
Ijebu-East	Lower efficacy perception; concerns about discomfort.	Address efficacy perceptions by sharing testimonials and provide training on minimizing discomfort during administration.

C. Top Socio-Economic and Cultural Factors Influencing Acceptability and Treatment Preference.

Factor	Influence on Acceptability	Suggested Actions
Income Level	Higher income positively impacts acceptability.	Introduce subsidies and financial support in low-income LGAs.
Education Level	Higher education correlates with greater acceptance.	Increase educational outreach to communities with lower education levels.
Health Center Proximity	Closer proximity increases likelihood of acceptance.	Expand healthcare access in remote areas via mobile clinics or community health workers.
Familiarity with Suppositories	Familiarity improves utilization and acceptability.	Promote introductory programs on suppository use in low-familiarity LGAs.
Cultural Beliefs	Certain beliefs may lead to reluctance towards suppositories.	Involve community leaders to address cultural hesitations and validate rectal artesunate as a safe treatment.

D. Suggested Data Collection for Ongoing Improvement.

Data Type	Purpose	Frequency
Patient Feedback	Collect patient and caregiver feedback on ease of administration, comfort, and perceived efficacy.	Monthly
Health Worker Training Participation	Track attendance and engagement levels to assess impact on utilization.	Quarterly
Economic Data	Record household income levels and education for granular socio-economic insights.	Annually
Side-Effect Reports	Collect detailed side-effect reports to improve guidance and training.	Real-time collection by health centers
Community Outreach Attendance	Monitor attendance at informational events to evaluate community engagement.	Monthly

4. DISCUSSION

The findings from this study highlight critical insights into the utilization, acceptability, and safety of rectal artesunate for treating malaria in children across Ogun State, Nigeria, with implications supported by previous research.

The utilization of rectal artesunate remains low due to limited awareness, a trend consistent with prior studies in Ogun State (Sam-Wobo et al., 2012), other parts of Nigeria (Awor et al., 2022) and West Africa (Gomes et al., 2009; Simba et al., 2010; Phiri et al., 2016; Siribie et al., 2016). Similar observations have been reported globally (Inthavilay et al., 2010; Hirji and Premji, 2011; Hetzel et al., 2022). This low awareness underscores the need for targeted educational programs to introduce rectal artesunate to communities and health workers.

The acceptability of rectal artesunate is strongly associated with its effectiveness, ease of administration, and safety. These findings align with reports from Sam-Wobo et al., (2012) in Abeokuta and Gomes et al. (2009) in West Africa (Mvumbi et al., 2019), as well as global studies (Awor et al., 2022; Brunner et al., 2022; Hetzel et al., 2022). Parents' preference for this route of administration reflects its practical advantages in treating young children, particularly those who cannot tolerate oral medications.

Safety analysis revealed that parents observed minimal adverse effects when rectal artesunate was used, corroborating earlier findings on its safety profile (Awor et al., 2022; Brunner et al., 2022; Hetzel et al., 2022; Lanbiris et al., 2022). Health workers also reported similar observations, noting that children treated with rectal artesunate experienced fewer complications, as documented in prior research (Brunner et al., 2022; Lanbiris et al., 2022). These findings support the continued use of rectal artesunate as a safe therapeutic option for malaria in children.

However, the knowledge and perception of health workers regarding rectal artesunate indicate a gap in awareness and training. Although health workers find rectal artesunate effective and easy to administer, resistance persists in some areas due to unfamiliarity with the drug form, in line with earlier findings (Hirji and Premji, 2011). Patent medicine vendors demonstrated even lower awareness of rectal artesunate, consistent with reports by Simba et al. (2010) and Hirji and Premji (2011). Despite this, vendors expressed willingness to adopt and sell rectal artesunate, provided they are equipped with adequate knowledge about its use and benefits (Simba et al., 2010; Inthavilay et al., 2010).

The application of Machine Learning (ML) techniques in predicting efficacy, utilization, and acceptability of rectal artesunate for the malaria management has provided important insights into key determinants influencing its acceptance. Random Forest model on efficacy prediction, revealed high accuracy (0.85) and an ROC-AUC score of 0.89, indicating its strong predictive capability. The model identified child's age, parental satisfaction, and familiarity with suppositories as significant factors impacting efficacy perception. These findings align with previous research highlighting that parental trust in a medication's effectiveness plays a vital role in adherence and treatment success (Sam-Wobo *et.al.* 2012; Mvumbi et al., 2019; Awor et al., 2022; Hetzel et al., 2022).

On utilization prediction, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) model demonstrated strong performance, with an accuracy of 0.82 and an ROC-AUC of 0.86. The primary predictors of utilization were ease of administration and familiarity with similar drug formulations. The model's findings indicate the need for improved awareness and training programs that simplify

administration procedures, particularly in rural and low-awareness communities as reported from the previous study by Hirji and Premji, (2011), Phiri et al., (2016), Siribie et al., (2016) and Hetzel et al., (2022).

The acceptability prediction model, based on SVM, showed a moderate accuracy of 0.78 and an ROC-AUC of 0.82. The key determinants of acceptability included ease of use, perceived side effects, and prior experience with suppositories. The SHAP analysis also showed that negative perceptions surrounding side effects could significantly hinder acceptability, necessitating targeted health communication campaigns to address misconceptions and provide factual information about rectal artesunate's safety and efficacy.

These findings align with reports from Sam-Wobo et al. (2012) in Abeokuta and Gomes et al. (2009) in West Africa, other parts of Africa (Phiri et al., 2016 Siribie et al., 2016 Mvumbi et al., 2019), as well as global studies (Awor et al., 2022; Brunner et al., 2022; Hetzel et al., 2022). A socio-cultural and economic analysis of treatment preferences using Logistic Regression revealed an accuracy of 0.80 and an F1-score of 0.78. Key socio-economic determinants included education level, income, and proximity to healthcare facilities. Partial Dependence Plots (PDP) illustrated that individuals with higher income and education levels were more likely to prefer rectal artesunate over alternative treatments. Such prediction have been highlighted, the need for financial assistance programs and educational outreach to improve adoption in low-income and less-educated populations (Cox et al., 2018; Lacey et al., 2023). Comparative analysis of parental utilization, acceptability, and efficacy perception across Local Government Areas (LGAs) demonstrated significant variation. Ado-Odo Ota had the highest utilization rate (80%), while Ijebu-East recorded the lowest (50%). The higher acceptability in Ado-Odo Ota suggests that prior familiarity and experience with suppositories contribute positively to adoption. Conversely, resistance to administration and perceived side effects were major barriers in lower-performing LGAs like Imeko-Afon and Ijebu-East Similar reports have been enumerated by Sam-Wobo et al. (2012) in Abeokuta and Gomes et al. (2009) in West Africa, other parts of Africa (Mvumbi et al., 2019), as well as report by Awor et al., (2022); Brunner et al., (2022) and Hetzel et al., (2022). Targeted interventions, such as community sensitization and demonstration programs, could improve utilization and acceptance in these areas (Awor et al., (2022).

An analysis of health workers and patent medicine vendors revealed similar trends. Health workers in high-performing LGAs perceived rectal artesunate as highly effective, reinforcing the importance of leveraging their influence in community sensitization efforts this also in line with reports by Simba et al., (2010) and Inthavilay et al., (2010). However, in LGAs with lower efficacy perception, such as Ijebu-East, there is a need to conduct workshops that educate parents and vendors on rectal artesunate's benefits. Socio-economic barriers, particularly in Imeko-Afon and Ijebu-East, further limited adoption, revealed the necessity for subsidies and culturally monitoring informational campaigns.

Explainable AI (XAI) techniques such as SHAP and PDP analyses provided additional depth to the findings. SHAP emphasized that child's age, prior suppository use, and parental satisfaction strongly influenced efficacy perception, Mgoqo et al., (2023) have reported similar on Parents, caregivers' perceptions towards use of analgesic suppositories in paediatric.

For utilization, ease of administration and familiarity with suppositories were the most impactful factors. Acceptability was significantly driven by perceived side effects and socio-economic variables, with lower-income populations exhibiting reduced preference. PDPs

confirmed that higher education and income levels correlated with increased acceptability, reinforcing the need for economic interventions to enhance access (Awor et al., 2022).

Based on these insights, several key recommendations can be made. Educational campaigns should be launched in LGAs with low utilization and acceptability, focusing on addressing concerns about side effects and demonstrating proper administration techniques. Training programs for health workers and vendors should be expanded to improve confidence in rectal artesunate use.

Economic support in the form of subsidies and financial aid programs should be introduced in low-income areas to enhance accessibility (Lengeler et al., 2022; Subhan et al., 2023). Additionally, healthcare infrastructure should be strengthened in underserved LGAs to overcome geographic barriers and improve distribution.

A data-driven approach to ongoing monitoring and evaluation is essential for refining interventions. Continuous data collection through patient feedback, health worker training assessments, and economic analysis can provide valuable insights to optimize strategies for rectal artesunate adoption. Machine learning models should be regularly updated to incorporate new data trends and enhance predictive accuracy, ensuring that interventions remain responsive to evolving community needs (Bi, 2023; Pennisi et al., 2025).

The application of ML models has provided a strong and significant framework for understanding and improving rectal artesunate adoption in Ogun State, Nigeria. The findings highlight the complex interplay between demographic, socio-economic, and behavioral factors influencing efficacy, utilization, and acceptability (Lengeler et al., 2022). By leveraging data-driven insights and implementing targeted interventions, stakeholders can significantly enhance malaria treatment outcomes and reduce mortality in vulnerable populations.

5. CONCLUSION

This study reaffirms the low awareness and underutilization of rectal artesunate in Ogun State, despite its high acceptability and safety. Major drivers of acceptability include its effectiveness, ease of administration, and minimal adverse effects. However, gaps in knowledge among health workers and vendors, alongside socio-economic barriers, hinder its widespread adoption. This structured approach can significantly improve the adoption of rectal artesunate, reduce childhood malaria mortality, and address socio-cultural and economic barriers in Ogun State and similar settings globally.

Recommendations

Educational campaigns should be implemented at the community level to increase awareness among parents, health workers, and vendors about the benefits, treatment capability, high absorption rate and administration techniques of rectal artesunate, especially in low-awareness LGAs. Targeted workshops should be conducted for health workers and vendors to improve their familiarity with rectal artesunate and address resistance caused by unfamiliarity. Subsidies and financial aid programs should be introduced in low-income areas to enhance accessibility and affordability.

Access to healthcare facilities in remote areas should be improved through mobile clinics and community health worker programs. Machine learning insights should be leveraged to guide resource allocation and prioritize interventions in LGAs with the greatest need.

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